

Impact of Indiscipline on Students' Academic Performance and School Management Strategies in Nigerian Public Secondary Schools

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Abstract

Background: Indiscipline, encompassing behaviours such as truancy, bullying, examination malpractice, and defiance of authority, poses significant challenges to the educational system.

Objective: This study investigates the impact of indiscipline on students' academic performance and school management strategies in Nigerian public secondary schools, focusing on Ekiti State.

Methodology: Four research questions guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. Data gathered through an instrument titled: Indiscipline and Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (ISAPQ), was analysed to discern the impact of indiscipline on students' academic performance and school management strategies. The results were presented in tables.

Results: The results showed that the prevalent indiscipline behaviour among students are frequent lateness to school, truancy, vandalism, disobedience and bullying. The contributing factors to indiscipline include a lack of parental supervision, inadequate teacher supervision and peer pressure. The impact of indiscipline was found to include disruption in the learning environment, school dropout rate, and poor academic performance. The management strategies include a reward system for compliant students, counselling services and punishment for offenders.

Unique Contributions: The study contributes to the need for collaborative efforts among stakeholders to address indiscipline and enhance academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools.

Conclusion: The study concludes that indiscipline negatively impacts students' academic performance.

Key Recommendations: The study recommends improving effective leadership, student monitoring, and fair disciplinary policies in secondary schools to curb indiscipline.

Keywords: Indiscipline, students' academic performance, public secondary schools

Introduction

Indiscipline refers to behaviours that deviate from established norms, rules, or codes of conduct within a group or society (Abang et al., 2024). It encompasses actions that disrupt the learning environment, hinder academic performance, and violate school policies in educational settings. Such behaviours may include absenteeism, tardiness, classroom disruptions, cheating, and plagiarism (Kamara et al., 2023; Mbon 2025). According to Silva et al. (2017), indiscipline is a student's behaviour, like disobeying school rules and norms of living standards with their teachers and peers. This definition highlights the relational aspect of indiscipline, emphasising how such behaviours affect interactions within the school community.

Indiscipline remains one of the pressing challenges facing educational systems worldwide, particularly in developing countries such as Nigeria. The causes of indiscipline in Nigerian public secondary schools are multifaceted. Research indicates that socio-economic factors, including poverty and broken homes, play a significant role in predisposing students to misbehaviour. Parental neglect, lack of supervision, and societal moral decay further compound the problem (Egwunyenga, 2009). At the school level, inadequate infrastructure, overcrowded classrooms, and inconsistent rule enforcement contribute to the prevalence of indiscipline.

In public secondary schools across Ekiti State, indiscipline among students has been identified as a critical factor undermining academic performance and overall school management effectiveness. Indiscipline manifests in various forms, including absenteeism, lateness, vandalism, bullying, examination malpractice, and lack of respect for school authorities. These behaviours hinder students' academic achievements and pose significant challenges to administrators striving to maintain an environment conducive to learning (Adeyemi & Adu, 2020).

The impact of indiscipline on students' academic performance is profound. Studies have shown that students in schools with high levels of indiscipline are more likely to underperform academically due to disrupted learning processes and reduced teacher productivity (Oluwatoyin, 2019). Similarly, indiscipline can lead to increased dropout rates, as students who repeatedly violate school rules are often suspended or expelled, thus losing critical instructional time. Truancy and lateness were major contributors to poor performance in secondary school students in southwestern Nigeria as Oko and Adie (2016) argue that students involved in examination malpractice are less likely to possess the critical thinking and problem-solving skills required for academic and life success. Moreover, teachers in schools plagued by indiscipline may experience burnout and reduced morale, further exacerbating the decline in the standards of academics (Ezeocha, 2021).

Indiscipline affects students' academic outcomes and poses significant challenges to school management. Effective school management relies on a conducive learning environment, which is disrupted by frequent acts of indiscipline. School administrators are often forced to spend substantial time addressing disciplinary issues rather than focusing on instructional leadership and curriculum implementation. In Ekiti State, factors such as inadequate parental involvement, poor teacher-student relationships, and a lack of proper disciplinary frameworks exacerbate the issue (Ogunbameru, 2020). However, the success of these strategies depends on adequate funding, professional training for school administrators, and consistent enforcement of rules and regulations.

In Ekiti State, the government has introduced various policies to address the challenges of indiscipline. Programmes promoting value education and teacher capacity-building workshops are among the strategies implemented to enhance school discipline. Despite these efforts, reports indicate that indiscipline persists, necessitating further research into innovative approaches tailored to the local context. This paper, therefore, explores the dual impacts of indiscipline on students' academic performance and school management in Nigerian public secondary schools, with a particular focus on Ekiti State. It also examines evidence-based strategies to mitigate these challenges, contributing to a more effective and sustainable education system.

Purpose of the Study

The study's core purpose is to investigate the impact of indiscipline on students' academic performance and school management strategies in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Identify the prevalent forms of indiscipline among Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.
- ii. Examine the factors contributing to indiscipline among students in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.
- iii. Investigate the impact of indiscipline on academic achievement among students in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.
- iv. Explore the school authorities' strategies for managing indiscipline in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Justification for the Study

Indiscipline remains a pervasive issue in Nigerian schools, with significant variations across states and regions. For instance, examination malpractice, absenteeism, and violence among students have raised concerns about the effectiveness of current school management strategies. According to Ogunsola et al. (2020), a fountain of knowledge has experienced declining academic performance in public examinations, partly attributed to indiscipline. To these scholars, addressing indiscipline is essential to reversing this trend and ensuring an environment is developed through a well-educated workforce. Students' academic performance is directly linked to the socio-economic development of a nation. Poor academic outcomes in public secondary schools have been associated with high rates of student indiscipline, which disrupts the learning environment and hampers educational goals.

Indiscipline, such as truancy, violence, and disruptions, negatively affects students' attitudes toward learning. These behaviours often result in poor academic outcomes, as indicated by consistently low Senior School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) performance. For instance, high failure rates in core subjects like Mathematics and English are linked to school indiscipline. Studies on peer pressure and truancy conducted in Ido/Osi Local Government Area of Ekiti State by Cambridge Research and Publications (2021), demonstrated that truancy and peer pressure are prominent forms of indiscipline that correlate strongly with poor academic performance. Students involved in these behaviours often miss critical instructional time, leading to gaps in learning and lower grades; research on school climate and discipline by the Ekiti State Ministry of Education (2022) shows that the nature of the school environment significantly impacts student outcomes. Controlled school climates on discipline were more prevalent in Ekiti State. These climates are associated with better academic performance than open or chaotic environments.

Theoretical Foundations

The present study has been extensively examined from a theoretical perspective. The theoretical foundation for this study incorporates behavioural theory, offering a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics between student behaviour, academic achievement, and school management strategies. Behaviourist theory, primarily developed by B.F. Skinner posits that behaviour is learned and reinforced through stimuli and consequences. In the context of indiscipline, students' disruptive behaviours are often reinforced by inadequate consequences or inconsistent application

of rules. This creates an environment where such behaviours persist and detract from the learning atmosphere, negatively impacting academic performance. Conversely, positive reinforcement strategies can encourage desirable behaviour and enhance the outcomes of students' academics (Akinwumi & Adigun, 2018). This theory highlights the importance of a multi-faceted approach to managing indiscipline. Effective strategies include implementing consistent behavioural policies, fostering positive relationships, engaging parents and communities, and addressing systemic challenges. In Ekiti State, where resources are often limited, following interventions to the specific needs and contexts of schools is important for improving discipline and academic performance.

Method

This study employs a quantitative research method using primary data sources, which involves a descriptive survey design to investigate the impact of indiscipline on students' academic performance and school management strategies in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State. A quantitative research method answers questions about descriptions among measured variables to explain, predict, and control phenomena. Teachers from the public secondary schools in Ekiti State served as the respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 320 respondents from the 3,203 total population in the public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The respondents were considered appropriate because they are in the best position to know the indiscipline among students and how management addresses it.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled: Indiscipline and Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (ISAPQ). The questionnaire was a modified four-point scale with a response method of Strongly Agree (SA) =4, Agree (A) =3, Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) =1. The structured questionnaire was adopted because of its efficacy in data collection, which attains a high cooperation rate, particularly among the students. Two professionals in educational evaluation from the Federal University Oye-Ekiti gave the questionnaire face and content validation to ensure the population's generalizability and appropriateness of the instrument's content.

The researchers administered and retrieved copies of the questionnaire from the respondents within Ekiti State in six (6) weeks. Three hundred twenty copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents selected for the study with proper supervision. However, a 100 per cent return rate was actualised because of good monitoring by the researchers. The returned copies of the questionnaire were collated and analysed using mean and standard deviation statistical tools. Ethical considerations were received from the Ministry of Education in Ekiti State. The guidelines were adhered to throughout the research process because of the involvement of human subjects in this research.

Results

The results of this study are presented below.

Research Question One: What are the prevalent forms of indiscipline among Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State?

Table 1: Analysis of Mean and Standard Deviation of the Responses on the Prevalent Forms of Indiscipline among Nigerian Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

S/NO	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Students often arrive late to school without valid reasons	3.47	0.50	Accepted
2	Truancy (frequent absenteeism) is a common problem in schools	3.52	0.51	Accepted
3	Vandalism of school property is a significant issue	3.40	0.47	Accepted
4	Students frequently disobey teachers' instructions in class	3.39	0.48	Accepted
5	Bullying among students is a major issue in this school	3.56	0.54	Accepted

N₁=320 respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 above identifies the prevalent forms of indiscipline among Nigerian public secondary schools. The results show total acceptance of the items. All items are prevalent forms of indiscipline among Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Table 2: Analysis of Mean and Standard Deviation of the Factors Contributing to Indiscipline among Students in Nigerian Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

S/NO	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Lack of parental supervision leads to student indiscipline.	3.25	0.41	Accepted
2	Economic hardship in the family influences students' behaviour negatively.	3.32	0.43	Accepted
3	The lack of effective disciplinary measures in schools encourages indiscipline	3.38	0.46	Accepted
4	Inadequate supervision by teachers leads to misconduct among students	3.22	0.40	Accepted
5	Peer pressure within the school environment leads to disruptive behaviour	3.51	0.50	Accepted

N₂=320 respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 examines the factors contributing to indiscipline among students in Nigerian public secondary schools. The results of the analysis indicate high acceptance. The acceptance of all items specifies that they contribute to indiscipline among students in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Table 3: Analysis of Mean and Standard Deviation of the Impact of Indiscipline on Academic Achievement in Nigerian Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

S/NO	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Disruption in the learning environment	3.38	0.46	Accepted
2	Poor attendance and dropout rates	3.57	0.55	Accepted
3	Low academic performance	3.58	0.56	Accepted
4	Negative teacher-student relationships	3.62	0.58	Accepted

N₃ = 320 respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 explores the impact of indiscipline on academic achievement in Nigerian public secondary schools. The results of the analysis show high acceptance. Accepting all items indicates that indiscipline leads to disruption in the learning environment, poor attendance and dropout rates, low academic performance, and negative teacher-student relationships in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Table 4: Analysis of Mean and Standard Deviation of the School Authorities' Strategies for Managing Indiscipline in Nigerian Public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State

S/NO	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
15	The school rewards students who exhibit exemplary behaviour	3.39	0.28	Accepted
16	The school adopts restorative practices to help students learn from their mistakes	3.58	0.43	Accepted
17	Teachers actively monitor student activities to prevent indiscipline	3.59	0.45	Accepted
18	The school provides regular counselling sessions for students to address behavioural challenges	3.71	0.48	Accepted
19	Punishments for breaking school rules are fairly and consistently enforced	3.80	0.42	Accepted

N₄ = 320 respondents

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4 explores the school authorities' strategies to manage indiscipline in Nigerian public secondary schools. The results of the analysis show high acceptance. The acceptance of all items indicates that those are the school authorities' strategies for managing indiscipline in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Discussion of Findings

This finding revealed the prevalent forms of indiscipline among Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The findings showed that arriving late to school without valid reasons, truancy, vandalism of school property, students' frequent disobedience of teachers' instructions in class, and bullying among students are the prevalent forms of indiscipline among Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State. The finding is upheld by Adeyemi and Adu (2020), who submitted that indiscipline manifests in various forms, including absenteeism, lateness, vandalism, bullying, examination malpractice, and lack of respect for school authorities. They further said that these behaviours not only hinder students' academic achievements but also pose significant challenges to administrators striving to maintain an environment conducive to learning. Truancy, or absenteeism without valid reasons, is one of the most common forms of indiscipline among students. It affects academic performance and increases the likelihood of school dropout (Ekundayo & Alonge, 2020).

The finding is in line with Ezeocha (2021), who affirmed that bullying often stems from a lack of effective disciplinary measures and the influence of societal violence. He stated that victims of bullying experience reduced self-esteem, poor academic performance, and, in severe cases, psychological trauma. It was discovered that disrespect for teachers and school administrators is increasingly prevalent. This behaviour often manifests as verbal abuse, refusal to follow instructions, or outright defiance. This finding corroborates Ajayi and Fasola (2019), who said that disrespect for teachers and school authorities is fueled by the breakdown of moral values and inadequate enforcement of school rules. To them, students who fail to respect authority contribute to classroom disruptions, making it difficult for educators to maintain discipline and deliver lessons effectively. Findings also support the study by Abang et al. (2024) that saw indiscipline encompasses actions that disrupt the learning environment, hinder academic performance, and violate school policies in educational settings. According to Kamara et al. (2023), such behaviour may include absenteeism, tardiness, classroom disruptions, cheating, and plagiarism.

It is important to note that the various forms of indiscipline in Nigerian public secondary schools have far-reaching implications for the education system and society. They compromise the quality of education, hinder students' personal development, and perpetuate a culture of impunity. However, indiscipline remains a pervasive challenge in Nigerian public secondary schools. Therefore, addressing this issue requires collective efforts from parents, educators, policymakers, and the wider community.

The findings revealed the factors contributing to indiscipline among students in Nigerian public secondary schools. The findings show that lack of parental supervision, economic hardship in the family, lack of effective school disciplinary measures, inadequate teacher supervision, and peer pressure within the school environment contribute to indiscipline among Nigerian public secondary school students in Ekiti State. Supporting the findings, previous studies show parental involvement in education correlates with student discipline; students from families with active parental engagement exhibit fewer behavioural issues (Epstein, 2011). Peer influence also plays a significant role; students who associate with delinquent peers are more likely to exhibit similar behaviours. The study conducted in Ekiti State by Ogunbameru (2020) affirmed that factors such as inadequate parental involvement, poor teacher-student relationships, and a lack of proper disciplinary frameworks exacerbate students' indiscipline.

The finding specified that indiscipline leads to disruption in the learning environment, poor attendance and dropout rates, low academic performance, and negative teacher-student relationships. Indiscipline among students creates distractions that hinder both teaching and learning. According to Brown (2020), frequent classroom disruption reduces instructional time and affects the ability of students to concentrate on lessons. Teachers spend significant time managing misbehaviour rather than engaging in effective instructional activities, leading to a decline in academic performance. Also, students who frequently skip classes miss essential lessons, assignments, and interactions with peers and teachers, leading to knowledge gaps and lower grades.

Studies have shown a direct relationship between student behaviour and academic achievement. Indiscipline, such as failing to complete homework, absenteeism, engaging in conflicts, and cheating, reduces academic motivation and effort, leading to poor performance in examinations and coursework (Mensah & Atta, 2022). Furthermore, students exhibiting indiscipline often lack self-regulation skills essential for academic success. Indiscipline frequently leads to strained relationships between students and teachers. When students display disrespectful behaviour, teachers may become less motivated to provide individualised support, impacting students' learning experiences and performance. Positive teacher-student relationships are crucial for academic motivation, and a lack thereof can result in disengagement from learning activities. According to Williams and Martinez (2023), promoting a culture of discipline through mentorship and student engagement programmes will help reduce disruptive behaviours and improve academic outcomes.

The finding revealed school authorities' strategies for managing indiscipline. The findings show that the school rewards students who exhibit exemplary behaviour, the school adopts restorative practices to help students learn from their mistakes, the school provides regular counseling sessions for students to address behavioural challenges, teachers actively monitor student activities to prevent indiscipline, and punishments for breaking school rules are fairly and consistently enforced are school authorities' strategies for managing indiscipline among students in Nigerian public secondary schools in Ekiti State.

The finding corroborates Gregory et al. (2016), who found that schools implementing restorative justice reported a 30% decline in disciplinary referrals, emphasizing the importance of dialogue and mutual respect. The researchers stated that restorative practices have gained significant attention in recent years as an alternative to punitive measures. They said the practices focus on repairing harm, fostering accountability, and rebuilding relationships. To them, restorative approaches reduce suspensions and expulsions, leading to a more inclusive school climate.

However, parental involvement in managing student discipline has proven effective in fostering a collaborative approach to behaviour management. Epstein (2011) argued that schools engaging parents in disciplinary processes experienced fewer behavioural issues, as students were more likely to internalise expected norms when reinforced at home. His study also found that teachers who underwent behavioural management training reported fewer disruptions and improved student engagement.

Conclusion

Indiscipline remains a significant challenge in Nigerian public secondary schools, particularly in Ekiti State, and has far-reaching consequences for students' academic performance and the overall effectiveness of school management. When students engage in acts of indiscipline such as truancy, cheating, bullying, and disobedience, it disrupts the learning environment, reduces instructional time, and negatively impacts academic outcomes. Additionally, it strains the capacity of school administrators to maintain order, allocate resources effectively, and implement teaching strategies that promote learning.

To address these challenges, school management must adopt proactive strategies, including fostering a positive school climate, engaging parents and guardians, and implementing clear, consistent disciplinary policies. Teachers and school administrators should have professional development programmes to handle behavioural issues constructively. Counselling services and peer mentoring programmes can also play a crucial role in curbing indiscipline by addressing its root causes, such as family problems, peer pressure, and socio-economic challenges.

Moreover, the collaboration between schools, communities, and government agencies is essential in reinforcing discipline and promoting a culture of academic excellence. By implementing these strategies, public secondary schools in Ekiti State can mitigate the impact of indiscipline, enhance academic performance, and create an environment conducive to holistic student development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. School authorities should enforce clear and concise, consistent rules that outline acceptable behaviour. These rules should be communicated effectively to all students and stakeholders.
2. School authorities should ensure that students understand the consequences of indiscipline through orientation programmes and regular assemblies.
3. Educational institutions should adopt proactive measures to instill discipline and create a conducive learning environment for academic success.
4. School authorities should recognise and reward well-behaved students to encourage others to emulate such behaviour.

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